

Developing Unpopular Sports through Grassroots Sports Promotion in Delta State; the Media as a Panacea

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Abstract

This paper examined the place of media in developing unpopular sports through grassroots sports promotion as a means of creating awareness for these unpopular sports at the grassroots. The paper also examined adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competition for developing sports through media in Delta state. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the paper with a sample size of 400 respondents. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The findings showed that organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness would develop sports in Delta State to a high extent and would significantly develop sports in Delta State. The result also revealed that adequate funding of unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media would help to develop sports to a high extent and would significantly improve sports development in Delta state. It was recommended that the local Government administrators should endeavour to organize seminar/workshops for schools to create awareness for these unpopular sports at the grassroots

Keywords: Developing, Grassroots sports, Media, Unpopular sports.

Introduction

Bamidele & Abu (2019) stated that human beings are born with natural instincts for sports. Alvarez (2019) suggested that sports have been a natural common cultural expression in the human being since the beginning of time. Body & Breeze (2016) have since explained that sport itself is a kind of adventure whose special quality puts sports in the position of being an attractive and exciting suitable for all. They further stated that decisions made by individuals to be involved on sports during childhood and adolescence stage help to build the person's identity. Alfonso & Jose (2015) and Singer (2019) noted that sports shape part of our daily life as individuals desire or wish to engage in one form of physical activity or the other on a daily bases, that during primitive time, sports was competition form by ethnics, values and survival. They further continued that in the recent times sports are an activity which promotes growth/development of healthy habit, entertainment and leisure.

Unpopular sports are sport that are going into extinction especially at the grassroots due

to the absence of sports facilities, equipment, personnel, funding and possibly lack of awareness. Body & Breeze (2016) and Singer (2020a) opined that the neglect of a sport leads to it being unpopular. Mohamed et al (2020) suggested that sports are an effective instrument in improving the capacity of the labour force. Unpopular sports make up the full circle of sports development and so if they are not encouraging these sports the development of sports will be crimping.

Table 1 shows some of these unpopular and popular sports in Delta State.

S/N	Popular	Unpopular
1	Football (soccer)	Squash
2	Basketball	Gymnastics
3	Boxing	Cricket
4	Tennis	Handball
5	Table tennis	Martial arts (judo, karate, taekwondo)

Grassroots Sports

According to Mogens (2011) grassroots sports is sport for all. Huiw, Honggang & Sonna (2019) opined that grassroots sports have social, cultural and economical benefits that help in the development of sports. Onifade (2011) and Singer (2020b) suggested that sports have gone beyond mere recreation to improving grassroots sports for national integration/prestige, international image, social limelight, economic growth and political power. For example the Okpepe race in Edo State has gradually titled awareness towards the grassroots sports of that area thus bringing development to sports, the community and the state. Grassroots sports uncountable, fosters the processes to scout for, identity, develop talents as well as raise fitness consciousness, mass participation in sports and recreation activities by individuals. To actualize this goal, grassroots sports Development Department (2009) was created and had the following as its main duties and responsibilities:

1. Guide the implementation of grassroots development policies to carefully increase the number and quality of talents in sports.
2. Initiate policies on grassroots sports development in the country.
3. Serve as a linkage between the ministry and grassroots to scout and select sports talent for the national team.
4. Coordinate and supervise the activities of the zonal offices.
5. Plan, organize and coordinate the national youth Games, amongst others.

Media as Panacea

Mehdi et al (2012) stated that Media is one of the basic instruments to inform, instruct, and examine social values. That Media helps to increase individual's knowledge and change individual's attitude positively about sports. They further stated that the major purpose of sport Media is to develop sports. Igwebuikwe (2021) opined that media have brought information closer to the people without restrictions, that they provide the avenue for people to share information

that can shape their opinions, attitude and decisions. Bakari(2017) stated that Nigeria government should put incentives in place to encourage sports investors both foreign and domestic, and that sports sectors need funds to ensure its success. Nwankwo & Ekechukwu (2017) and Dugalic & Krsteska (2013) opined that the lack of funds is attributed to the poor management in sports, that little or nothing is set aside for sports facilities equipment or other affairs of sports. They further explained that sports funds provided by government are usually not enough to get good results in the sporting sector in the country. Bamidele & Abu (2020) suggest that the Nigeria school sports federation (NSSF) has been the pillar for the nation's grassroots sports development programme because great athletes of the country have being produced as such sports at the grassroots level need funding as a way of encouragement for continuity especially through advertisement(media).

Singer (2019) stated that federal and state governments fail to accept primary responsibility of funding sports for youth at the grassroots level for youth development in Nigeria. That responsibility had not been discharged through regular and adequate budgetary allocations to the sports sector. He explained that financial support, training, advertisement such as creating awareness through media and facilities need to be provided at all levels in order to ensure youth participation. Mohammed (2018) and Diejomaoh, Akarah, & Tayire (2015) emphasized that if set goals were to be achieved, adequate funding is essential for effective sport development. Morgan & Dube(2018) added that most government owned facilities are affected by budget deficits hence most of them are dilapidated just as lack of funding has resulted in the grassroots sports being underdeveloped. Gafoor (2012) suggested that awareness is the state or ability to perceive, the state of being aware of something. He further stated that to be aware means to know, to realize or be interested in knowing about something. Amelia (2021) added that media is a communication tool used to deliver information such as news media, print media, television movies amongst others. He continued that social media is a digital tool that allows users to quickly and easily create and share content with the public.

Esther & Rodgers (2021) postulated that personal advertising is a type of promotion that involves face to face persuasion to sell a product for example: door to door or home/mouth to mouth demonstrations. They further stated that these are the types of advertising needed to make unpopular sports improve at the grassroots in developing them. In this type of communication consumers see the images and tend to ask questions which bring about explanation. In this course of explanation one can influence and persuade people to come participate actively or passively during the competitions of these unpopular sports. Bandana & Daya (2022) suggest that all advertising contains both information and persuasion that the symbols and signs used should be understood in the same way to both source and receiver. They further noted that any message that is formulated should be in a manner that gains maximum attention of the receiver (fans). Also the message should be able to arouse the awareness of the people (fans). Sretenka (2018) opined that modern sports, of which unpopular sport is part of cannot function without influencing sports through media and funding.

Method

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study with a population of 222,207 from which a sample size of 400 respondents was drawn comprised of 224 students who were randomly sampled through balloting while the 80 principals and 96 sports personnel were purposively sampled from five (5) schools selected through balloting in the 16 local government areas. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The instrument for the study is a self-structured questionnaire which comprised of two (2) sections. Section A comprised of 3 items seeking information on respondents' demographics and section B comprised of 44 items rated on a four (4) point modified Likert type rating scale of Very High (VH) 4 points, High (H) 3 points, Low (L) 2 points and Very Low (VL) 1 point which content validity was established through factor analysis and an internal consistency reliability index (r) of 0.78 established with the Cronbach Alpha. Data collected were analysed using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software version 23 to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A criterion mean value of 2.50 was used to determine the extent.

Research Question one: To what extent would sports programme awareness for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions towards sports development in Delta state of Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on sports programme awareness for organizing unpopular grassroots sport competitions towards sports development in Delta State of Nigeria.

Findings and Discussion

S/N	ITEMS	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	Mea n	SD	Decision
1.	The extent to which sports activities included in the school prospectus to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	117 29.3%	193 48.3%	89 22.3%	1 0.3%	3.07	0.72	High
2.	The extent to which pictorial illustrations on note book front/back cover and T-shirts for awareness of unpopular grassroots sports will develop sports is	116 29%	93 23%	152 38%	39 9.8%	2.27	0.99	High

3.	The extent to which workshops organized by school sports personnel to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	205 51.3%	65 16.3%	61 15.3%	69 17.3%	3.02	1.17	High
4.	The extent to which workshops organized by Local Government Administrators to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	205 51.3%	65 16.3%	61 15.3%	69 17.3%	3.02	1.17	High
5.	The extent to which workshops organized by State Sport Councils to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	146 36.5%	119 29.8%	135 33.8%	0 0%	3.03	0.84	High
GRAND MEAN						2.88	0.98	High

Table 2: Shows the respondents' response trend from items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 on sports programme awareness for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions towards sports development in Delta state of Nigeria with mean values between 2.27 and 3.07 and standard deviation between 0.72 and 1.17 indicating a high extent. However, the grand mean value for items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 is 2.88 above the criterion mean value of 2.50 with a standard deviation of 0.98. It is therefore concluded that the extent to which sports programme awareness for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions would develop sports in Delta state of Nigeria is high.

Research Question two: To what extent would adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions develop sports through media in Delta State of Nigeria?

Table 3 Mean and standard deviation on adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions would develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	VHE	HE	LE	VLE	Mea n	SD	Decision
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6.	The extent to which funding grassroots sports competitions in schools will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is	143 35.8%	142 35.5%	115 28.8%	0 0%	3.07	0.8	High
7.	The extent to which funding grassroots sports competitions by host communities will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is	121 30.3%	108 27%	148 37%	23 5.7%	2.82	0.93	High
8.	The extent to which Local Government funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is	154 38.5%	120 30%	126 31.5%	0 0%	3.07	0.84	High
9.	The extent to which State Government sports councils funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is	154 38.5%	122 28%	134 33.5%	0 0%	3.03	0.85	High
10.	The extent to which Private organizations' funding of	132 33%	147 36.8%	120 30%	1 0.3%	3.03	0.80	High

	grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is							
11.	The extent to which Individuals' funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is	162 40.3%	126 31.5%	112 28%	0 0%	3.13	0.82	High
	GRAND MEAN					3.03	0.84	High

Table 3 Shows the respondents' response trend for items 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 on adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions towards sports development through media in Delta state of Nigeria with mean values between 2.82 and 3.13 and standard deviation between 0.80 and 0.85 indicating high extent. However, the grand mean value for items 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 is 3.03 above the criterion mean value of 2.50 with a standard deviation of 0.84. It is therefore concluded that the extent to which adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media would develop sports in Delta state of Nigeria is high.

Hypothesis one: Organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness would not significantly develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria.

Table 4: Linear regression analysis on organizing unpopular grassroots sports competition sports programme awareness towards sports development in Delta State of Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.88 ^a	.80	.77	11.031

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	106601.657	4	26650.414	201.409	.000 ^b
1	Residual	52266.343	395	132.320		
	Total	158868.000	399			

Coefficient^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized t Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	111.173	41.575		2.674	.000
The extent to which sports activities included in the school prospectus to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	7.840	8.058	.049	.973	.000
The extent to which pictorial illustrations on schools fences for awareness of unpopular grassroots sports will develop sports is	12.546	5.866	.107	2.139	.000
1 The extent to which workshops organized by school sports personnel to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	7.667	4.963	.077	1.545	.000
The extent to which workshops organized by Local Government Administrators to promote awareness of unpopular sports will develop sports is	2.683	6.904	.019	.389	.000

The results in table 4 shows a linear regression output on organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness towards sports development in Delta State of Nigeria with a computed F-value of 201.41 and a P-value of 0.00. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level (α -level) of 0.05, the P-value of 0.00 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null

hypothesis was rejected. This implies that, organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness would significantly develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria. The R-Square adjusted value of 0.77 indicates 77% of variance in organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness accounting for sports development in Delta State of Nigeria. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for sports development in the State from organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness for the four (4) items was 7.84, 12.55, 7.67 and 2.68 while the standardized coefficient (β) for the four (4) items was 0.05, 0.11, 0.08 and 0.19. The t-values for the four (4) items are 0.97, 2.14, 1.55 and 0.39. It was therefore concluded that organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness would significantly develop sports at alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis two: Adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media would not significantly develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria.

Table 5: Linear regression analysis on adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions towards sports development through media in Delta State of Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.980 ^a	.870	.810	11.178

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	562635.521	6	93772.587	772.484	.000 ^b
	Residual	47706.479	393	121.391		
	Total	610342.000	399			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	15.740	45.070		.349	.000

The extent to which adequate funding grassroots sports competitions in schools will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is

10.221	7.008	.071	1.459	.000
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The extent to which grassroots sports competitions by host communities will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is 30.153 5.959 .243 5.060 .000

The extent to which Local Government funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is 38.60 7.725 .028 .500 .000

The extent to which State Government sports councils funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is 13.701 6.624 .101 2.068 .000

The extent to which private organizations' funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is 8.50 6.954 .006 .122 .000

The extent to which individuals' funding of grassroots sports competitions will enhance participation in unpopular sports for sports development is 23.213 7.827 .164 2.966 .000

The result in table 5 shows a linear regression output on adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions towards sports development through media in Delta States of Nigeria with a computed F-value of 772.484 and a P-value of 0.00. Testing the hypothesis at alpha level (α -level) of 0.05, the P-value of 0.00 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that, adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media in schools would significantly develop sports in Delta States of Nigeria. The R-Square adjusted value of 0.81 indicates 81% of variance in adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media accounting for sports development in Delta State of Nigeria. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for sports development in the states from adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media for the six (6) items was 10.22, 30.15, 38.60, 13.70, 8.50 and 23.21 while the standardized coefficient (β) for the six (6) items was 0.07, 0.24, 0.03, 0.10, 0.01 and 0.16. The t-values for the six (6) items are 1.46, 5.06, 0.50, 2.07, 0.12 and 0.297. It was thus concluded that adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media would significantly develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria at an alpha level of 0.05.

Discussion of Result

The findings of the research showed that organizing unpopular grassroots sport competitions programme awareness would develop sports in Delta State to a high extent and that organizing unpopular grassroots sports competitions programme awareness in Delta State would significantly develop sports in Delta State. The findings of the research are in line with Emmanuel (2021) who stated that advertisements are used to create awareness of a product (sports) and also the exposure of these unpopular sports. He further explained that advertisement is a promotional strategy to create awareness of a product (sports) as it is a powerful communication force for creating awareness which is an important tool of marketing sport. The finding also showed that adequate funding of unpopular grassroots sports competitions through media would develop sports in Delta State to a high extent and that adequate funding of unpopular grassroots sports through media would significantly develop sports in Delta State of Nigeria.

The findings of this study is also in line with Nwankwo & Ekechukwu (2017) who stated that funding is essential for any sports programme to be run effectively and that adequate funding makes sports programme to be successful. The finding is also in line with Ekpo (2013) who noted that the development of sports depends on adequate funding and that when there is a lack of funding, no sports programme can be sustained. Mohammed et al (2018) noted that funding is the major element which many things depend on and that for any sports programme to be organized it becomes a prerequisite for such conditions as payment for facilities and equipment, advertising, payment for sports administrator/personnel amongst others to be attained.

Conclusion

The findings of this research have revealed that programme awareness organization at the grassroots would develop unpopular sports in Delta State to a high extent and would significantly develop sport in Delta State. It was also concluded that adequate funding for organizing unpopular grassroots sports competition through media would help to develop sports to a high extent and significantly improve sports towards sports development in Delta state.

Recommendation

Unpopular grassroots sports need advertising and funding in promoting these sports so as to develop sports in Delta State.

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